

A Compact Spiking Neural Network for Real-Time Swimming Style Recognition on Low-Power FPGA

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Abstract. Accurate and energy-efficient recognition of swimming styles is essential for real-time training analysis in wearable systems. This work introduces an end-to-end, spike-driven approach for swimming style classification, in which a Spiking Neural Network (SNN) operates on event-based inertial inputs. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first application of neuromorphic computing to swimming style recognition.

The signal encoding employs delta modulation on accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer axes, converting continuous sensor streams into sparse binary spike trains that capture temporal dynamics of swimming movements without requiring explicit filtering or feature extraction. A compact fully connected SNN with leaky integrate-and-fire neurons classifies four swimming styles (freestyle, breaststroke, backstroke, and butterfly) using only 18,176 trainable parameters.

The approach is validated on a publicly available benchmark of 40 swimmers recorded in realistic training conditions, achieving an F1 of 0.945 under Leave-One-Subject-Out cross-validation.

To support deployment on resource-constrained wearable devices, we implement an optimized hardware architecture on a low-power Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA. The event-driven nature of the SNN enables efficient inference by processing only active spikes, reducing power consumption while maintaining low latency. Performance evaluations indicate an execution time of 7.8 ms per classification, with energy usage of 93.6 μJ , demonstrating the feasibility of on-device real-time swimming analysis.

Keywords: Spiking neural networks · Real-time monitoring · Edge computing · Sport analytics.

1 Introduction

Wearable devices equipped with inertial measurement units (IMUs) have become a standard tool for monitoring athletic performance [3]. Modern smartwatches integrate accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers [1] capable of capturing multi-axis motion at sampling rates suitable for human activity recognition [2].

Among individual sports, swimming presents a particularly compelling use case: each stroke style exhibits distinctive cyclic kinematic patterns that are well-suited for automatic classification from wrist-worn inertial sensors [1]. Accurate real-time recognition of swimming styles enables objective training analysis, automatic lap counting, and personalized feedback, replacing manual observation by coaches. However, deploying such classification systems on battery-powered wearables imposes strict constraints on computational cost and power consumption, as continuous processing of multi-axis sensor streams must be sustained over extended training sessions. In swimming, this challenge is compounded by the strong attenuation of radio-frequency signals in water, which limits wireless data transfer from submerged sensors [8] and demands fully on-device inference.

Several deep learning approaches have been proposed for swimming style recognition from smartwatch sensor data. Brunner et al. [1] established the primary public benchmark of 40 swimmers, on which subsequent CNN and LSTM architectures [17, 14] have achieved high classification accuracy. However, these models rely on dense floating-point computation with large parameter counts, and none addresses deployment on ultra-low-power wearable hardware suitable for continuous on-device inference.

Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) offer a fundamentally different computing paradigm in which neurons communicate through sparse, asynchronous binary events (spikes) rather than continuous-valued activations [13]. Computation is triggered only when input changes exceed a significance threshold, making SNNs inherently suited for event-driven processing of temporal signals. In this work, we apply delta modulation to accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer axes, converting continuous inertial streams into sparse binary spike trains that capture the temporal dynamics of swimming movements without requiring explicit filtering or handcrafted feature extraction. The resulting event-based representation naturally matches the SNN computation model: the network processes only active spikes, achieving high sparsity throughout the inference pipeline. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first application of neuromorphic computing to swimming style recognition.

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the proposed system. Raw inertial signals from a wrist-worn smartwatch are encoded into binary spike trains via delta modulation applied to accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer data. A compact four-layer fully connected SNN with Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) neurons classifies four swimming styles (freestyle, backstroke, breaststroke, and butterfly) from the encoded spikes. The entire pipeline, from encoding to classification, is deployed on the open-source SYNTzulu platform [11], targeting a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA).

To summarize, this work presents the following main contributions:

- We introduce the first neuromorphic approach for swimming style classification, employing a compact LIF-based SNN to classify four swimming styles from wrist-worn smartwatch IMU data.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed swimming style classification system. Raw inertial signals (accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer) from a wrist-worn smartwatch are encoded into sparse binary spike trains via per-axis delta modulation (24 channels). A four-layer fully connected SNN with LIF neurons classifies four swimming styles. The entire pipeline is deployed on a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA via the SYNtzulu platform.

- We apply delta modulation encoding to multi-sensor inertial data (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer), producing 24 sparse binary spike channels that preserve temporal dynamics without explicit feature engineering.
- We validate the approach on a publicly available benchmark of 40 swimmers under LOSO cross-validation, achieving an F1 of 0.945 with temporal voting, within 3 percentage points of the state-of-the-art CNN [1].
- We demonstrate deployment on a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA via the SYNtzulu platform, achieving real-time inference in 7.8 ms with 93.6 μJ energy consumption per classification, enabling always-on monitoring on ultra-low-power wearable devices.

2 Related Work

Wearable inertial sensors have become increasingly prevalent in sport analytics, enabling continuous monitoring of athletic performance outside laboratory settings [3]. The standard approach to sensor-based activity recognition segments continuous data streams into fixed-length sliding windows, from which a classifier predicts the activity label [2]. Deep learning methods, particularly convolutional and recurrent neural networks, have largely superseded handcrafted feature pipelines in this domain, achieving high accuracy across a variety of sports and daily activities, including swimming style recognition [1, 17, 5, 19]. Swimming is a particularly well-suited target for IMU-based recognition, as the four competitive strokes produce distinct cyclic kinematic patterns at the wrist that differ in arm trajectory, body rotation, and stroke frequency.

Brunner et al. [1] established the primary benchmark for swimming style recognition by collecting 17 hours of smartwatch sensor data from 40 swimmers. Their four-layer CNN with approximately 128,000 parameters achieves an F1 of 0.974 under 40-fold LOSO cross-validation on five classes (four strokes plus

transitions), employing four data augmentation techniques and an 83% window overlap. Tarasevicius and Serackis [17] applied a three-layer bidirectional LSTM to the same dataset under the same LOSO protocol, reaching an F1 of 0.914 without data augmentation. Meng [14] improved per-class accuracies to 97.4–98.8% with an enhanced CNN under the same protocol.

Beyond the Brunner dataset, several works have addressed swimming recognition with different sensor placements. Delhaye et al. [5] placed a single IMU at the sacrum and trained a Bi-LSTM to classify eight swimming activities, reporting an F1 of 0.96 after post-processing on a single hold-out subject. Zhang et al. [19] combined a 1D-CNN with a Bi-LSTM and attention on hip-mounted data from four coaches, reaching 93.53% accuracy. Hamidi Rad et al. [9] applied rule-based thresholds on multiple body-worn sensors, highlighting the difficulty of wrist-based classification without learned features. Zhuang and Xue [20] improved accuracy by 3.9 percentage points through periodic matching that segments signals by stroke cycle. Across all these works, the models rely on dense floating-point computation, and none explores event-driven or neuromorphic processing.

Deploying these models on ultra-low-power wearable hardware remains an open challenge, as continuous on-device inference demands power budgets in the order of tens of milliwatts. Yeon et al. [18] demonstrated general activity recognition on an Apple Watch GPU with approximately 7 million parameters and 21.1 ms total inference; however, smartwatch-class processors typically consume hundreds of milliwatts, limiting battery life for continuous monitoring. These constraints motivate the exploration of alternative computing paradigms that can reduce both model size and inference energy.

SNNs offer one such paradigm, in which neurons communicate through sparse binary events rather than dense real-valued activations [13, 15]. This event-driven computation model inherently exploits the temporal sparsity of sensor signals: inference cost scales with the number of active spikes rather than the total number of synapses, enabling substantial energy savings when input activity is sparse. Delta modulation provides a natural interface between continuous sensor streams and SNN inputs by encoding signal changes that exceed a fixed threshold as binary spike events, preserving temporal dynamics while suppressing redundant information. Recent work has shown that SNNs can match or approach ANN accuracy on activity recognition tasks at a fraction of the computational cost, with applications to wearable human activity recognition [12], energy-efficient early-exit inference [7], and event-driven action recognition [4]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work has applied SNNs to swimming style recognition or, more broadly, to sport-specific activity classification from wearable inertial sensors.

FPGA platforms offer a practical middle ground between the flexibility of general-purpose processors and the efficiency of custom ASICs, with reconfigurable logic that can be adapted as SNN architectures evolve [11]. In our previous work [16], we demonstrated the viability of this approach for wearable biosignal processing, deploying an SNN for real-time sEMG gesture recognition

Table 1. Class distribution of the Brunner et al. dataset [1]. The four swimming styles exhibit a pronounced imbalance in the number of swimmers who performed each style. Only 18 out of 40 swimmers performed all four styles.

Style	Swimmers
Freestyle	39
Breaststroke	24
Backstroke	37
Butterfly	23
All 4 styles	18

on a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA at 11.3 mW inference power and 44.6 μJ per classification. This device provides 5,280 look-up tables and 128 KB of single-port RAM at an operating power in the order of 10 mW, making it a suitable target for always-on wearable inference.

3 Method

In this section, we describe the proposed swimming style classification system. We introduce the reference dataset, detail the spike-based encoding scheme, present the SNN architecture and training procedure, and define the evaluation protocol.

3.1 Dataset

This study employs the publicly available swimming dataset introduced by Brunner et al. [1], which comprises 17 hours of smartwatch sensor data collected from 40 swimmers in an indoor swimming pool. Recordings were acquired using a commercial wrist-worn smartwatch, capturing five sensor modalities: three-axis accelerometer (ACC), gyroscope (GYRO), magnetometer (MAG), barometric pressure, and ambient light, resampled to a uniform 30 Hz.

The dataset annotates four competitive swimming styles (freestyle, breaststroke, backstroke, and butterfly) alongside transition periods encompassing rest phases and wall turns. We retain only the four stroke labels and discard transition segments, reducing the classification task to four classes, whereas prior works on this benchmark evaluate five [17, 14]. The class distribution is notably imbalanced: freestyle is the most represented style, performed by 39 out of 40 swimmers, whereas butterfly is absent in 17 swimmers and breaststroke in 16. Only 18 out of 40 swimmers recorded all four styles during their sessions. Table 1 summarizes the per-class swimmer coverage.

From the five available sensor modalities, we select accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer (3 sensors), discarding pressure and ambient light. The three retained sensors capture complementary aspects of wrist kinematics (linear acceleration, angular velocity, and orientation), and Brunner et al. [1] reported

Algorithm 1: Delta Encoding with Reset

Input: Normalized signal $x = [x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{T-1}]$, threshold δ
Output: Binary spike trains s^+ and s^- of length T
 $\ell \leftarrow x_0$; // Initialize reference level
for $t \leftarrow 1$ **to** $T - 1$ **do**
 if $x_t - \ell \geq \delta$ **then**
 $s_t^+ \leftarrow 1$;
 $\ell \leftarrow x_t$; // Positive spike, reset reference
 else if $x_t - \ell \leq -\delta$ **then**
 $s_t^- \leftarrow 1$;
 $\ell \leftarrow x_t$; // Negative spike, reset reference
end

that excluding pressure and light does not degrade classification accuracy. For each sensor, we extract three spatial axes and compute the Euclidean magnitude, yielding 4 signals per sensor and 12 signals in total before encoding.

3.2 Signal Preprocessing and Encoding

Prior to spike generation, each sensor’s raw signals are normalized by dividing by a physical-unit constant that brings the three modalities into comparable ranges: accelerometer values are divided by 9.81 (gravitational acceleration in m/s^2), gyroscope values by π (maximum expected angular velocity in rad/s), and magnetometer values by 18 (empirically determined scale in μT). This per-sensor normalization preserves the relative dynamics within each modality while avoiding global z-score standardization.

The normalized signals are converted into binary spike trains using delta modulation, a well-established technique that encodes signal changes exceeding a fixed threshold as discrete binary events. As detailed in Algorithm 1, the encoder maintains a reference level ℓ initialized to the first sample. At each subsequent time step t , if the signal exceeds the reference by at least δ , a positive spike is emitted and the reference is reset to the current signal value; symmetrically, if the signal falls below the reference by at least δ , a negative spike is produced and the reference is updated. Time steps where neither condition is met generate no spike.

Delta encoding is applied independently to each of the 12 signals (three axes plus magnitude for each of the 3 sensors), with a fixed threshold $\delta = 0.05$ in normalized units. Each signal produces two spike trains (one for positive and one for negative threshold crossings), yielding $12 \times 2 = 24$ binary input channels. With $\delta = 0.05$, the average spike rate at the input layer is approximately 40% per channel, indicating a relatively dense input regime; the computational savings from spike sparsity arise primarily in the hidden layers, as discussed in Section 5.3.

Figure 2 illustrates the encoding process on a representative freestyle segment. The encoded spike trains are segmented into fixed-length windows of 6 sec-

Fig. 2. Delta encoding of a representative freestyle segment. Left: normalized accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer signals (three spatial axes per sensor). Right: corresponding binary spike trains produced by delta modulation with $\delta = 0.05$, with one positive and one negative channel per axis. The spike trains capture the temporal dynamics of the cyclic stroke pattern while suppressing constant-level intervals.

onds (180 time steps at 30 Hz) with 50% overlap between consecutive windows. Each window is assigned the label of the majority class among its constituent samples, provided that this class accounts for at least 80% of the samples within the window. Windows that do not meet this purity criterion are discarded.

3.3 SNN Topology and Training

The proposed classifier is a 4-layer fully connected spiking neural network with LIF neurons, implemented using the SpikingJelly framework [6]. The network receives 24 input channels and produces 4 output neurons corresponding to the swimming styles. The three hidden layers (of 64, 128, and 64 neurons) are interposed between the input and output layers, each consisting of a fully connected (dense) synapse followed by a LIF neuron. Table 2 details the layer dimensions and the resulting parameter count.

Each LIF neuron integrates incoming weighted spikes into a membrane potential v that decays exponentially between time steps. The membrane dynamics, governed by a decay factor $\alpha = 1 - 1/\tau$ (where τ is the membrane time constant),

Table 2. Topology of the proposed 4-layer SNN. Each layer consists of a fully connected (dense) synapse without bias followed by a LIF neuron. The total number of trainable parameters (synaptic weights only) is 18,176.

Layer	Input	Output	Parameters
Dense + LIF 1	24	64	$24 \times 64 = 1,536$
Dense + LIF 2	64	128	$64 \times 128 = 8,192$
Dense + LIF 3	128	64	$128 \times 64 = 8,192$
Dense + LIF 4	64	4	$64 \times 4 = 256$
Total			18,176

follow the update rule of Equation 1,

$$v'(t) = \alpha \cdot v(t) + \sum_i w_i \cdot s_i^{\text{in}}(t) \quad (1)$$

where w_i denotes the synaptic weight from presynaptic neuron i and $s_i^{\text{in}}(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ is its input spike at time t . When the updated potential exceeds the firing threshold θ , the neuron emits an output spike and the potential is reduced by θ through a soft reset (Equations 2-3).

$$v(t+1) = \begin{cases} v'(t), & \text{if } v'(t) < \theta \\ v'(t) - \theta, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$s^{\text{out}}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } v'(t) \geq \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In our configuration, the time constant is set to $\tau = 2.0$ and the firing threshold to $\theta = 1.0$. Gradient computation through the non-differentiable spike function employs a sigmoid-based surrogate.

Training is conducted using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} and a mini-batch size of 16. A plateau-based learning rate schedule monitors validation accuracy with a patience of 5 epochs: when no improvement is observed, the learning rate is multiplied by 0.5, for a maximum of 5 reductions. Training terminates via early stopping when the patience of 10 epochs is exhausted after the final learning rate reduction.

The loss function operates on the average output spike rate over the temporal window. A target spike-rate vector drives the true-class neuron toward 0.2 spikes per time step and all others toward 0.03; the mean squared error between observed and target rates defines the per-sample loss. At inference time, the class with the highest average firing rate is selected as the prediction.

Two data augmentation strategies are applied to improve generalization. First, the training set in each LOSO fold exhibits significant class imbalance, with freestyle windows outnumbering butterfly by up to $6\times$; minority classes are therefore oversampled by randomly duplicating windows with replacement until

all classes match the majority count, yielding a balanced training set per fold. Second, LOSO analysis reveals that one swimmer (S33) exhibits an anomalous sensor orientation (inverted gyroscope axis), causing systematic misclassification; to address this, we apply random axis flipping during training of the S33 fold, where each of the 9 sensor axes is independently sign-inverted with 50% probability, producing 4 augmented copies per window. The remaining 39 folds use oversampling only.

To prepare the network for deployment on the SYNtzulu accelerator, all synaptic weights are quantized to signed 8-bit integers using per-layer symmetric scaling. Each weight matrix is multiplied by $s = 127 / \max |w|$, rounded to the nearest integer, and divided back by s . This representation is natively supported by the 8-bit accumulation pipeline (Section 4), as evaluated in Section 5.3.

3.4 Evaluation Protocol

Model performance is assessed using LOSO cross-validation, the standard evaluation protocol for this dataset [1, 17, 14], which quantifies inter-subject generalization across the full swimmer population.

In the LOSO configuration, 40 folds are constructed, each leaving one swimmer out as the test set. Within each fold, 5 swimmers are drawn from the training pool as a validation set, selecting subjects that collectively cover all available classes, and the remaining swimmers constitute the training set. A separate model is trained from scratch for each fold.

Classification performance is reported using two metrics: overall accuracy (proportion of correctly classified windows) and macro-averaged F1 score (hereafter F1). To ensure comparability with Brunner et al. [1], we adopt their evaluation methodology: per-class F1 scores are first averaged within each swimmer, and the resulting per-swimmer F1 values are then averaged across all swimmers.

In addition to per-window classification, we evaluate temporal majority voting as a post-processing step, where the most frequent label over a sliding window of consecutive predictions is selected as the final output. The effect of different voting window sizes is analyzed in Section 5.

4 FPGA Deployment

To deploy the proposed classification pipeline on an ultra-low-power wearable device while leveraging the advantages of event-driven processing, we target the SYNtzulu platform, an open-source SNN processor designed for low-end FPGA implementation [11]. This device provides 5,280 Logic Cells (LCs), 128 KB of Single-Port RAM (SPRAM), 30 Embedded Block RAM (EBR) modules of 4 Kbit each, and 8 DSP blocks, at a typical operating power in the order of 10 mW.

The processor follows a System-on-Chip (SoC) architecture that integrates three main components. A RISC-V core based on the SERV microarchitecture [10] handles supervisory tasks, input/output peripheral management (sensor

Fig. 3. Architecture of the SYNTzulu SNN processor configured for swimming style classification. The system integrates a RISC-V core (SERV) for supervisory tasks, an encoding slot that performs delta modulation on 12 IMU signals to produce 24 binary spike channels, an SNN accelerator with two pipelined neuron modules executing the 4-layer LIF network, and a decoding slot that accumulates per-class spike rates to output the predicted swimming style. All synaptic weights are quantized to 8-bit and stored in on-chip SPRAM.

communication via SPI, classification output via UART), and system initialization, chosen for its minimal resource footprint. Two design-time configurable processing slots, termed *encoding* and *decoding* slots, implement the conversion of input sensor samples into binary spikes and the interpretation of output spikes into a classification result, respectively. An SNN accelerator module executes network inference in a clock-driven scheme while exploiting the event-based nature of spike inputs. The accelerator incorporates two pipelined neuron modules that share the workload by each processing half of the neurons in every layer. Each module accumulates four 8-bit synaptic weights per clock cycle, computes synaptic currents, updates membrane potentials according to LIF dynamics (Equations 1–3), and generates output spikes. An address generator module enables event-driven computation by dynamically fetching only the weights associated with active input synapses, skipping inactive channels and reducing the effective execution time in proportion to input sparsity.

Figure 3 illustrates the SYNTzulu architecture as configured for the swimming classification task. The encoding slot implements the delta modulation algorithm described in Section 3.2 independently on each of the 12 normalized IMU signals, producing 24 spike channels. A circular buffer continuously stores the most recent 180 spike vectors, occupying 4,320 bits (540 bytes), which fits within two EBR blocks. The decoding slot implements per-class spike-rate accumulation over the classification window, selecting the class with the highest average firing rate as the predicted swimming style.

The synaptic weights are represented in 8-bit fixed-point format and stored in on-chip SPRAM, occupying 18.4 KB of the available 128 KB capacity. Table 3

Table 3. Resource utilization of the swimming classification system on the Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA.

Resource	Used	Available	Utilization
Logic Cells (LC)	3,718	5,280	70.4%
DSP Blocks	2	8	25%
EBR (4 Kbit)	20	30	66.7%
SPRAM (32 KB)	4	4	100%

reports the resource utilization of the swimming classification system on the iCE40-UltraPlus.

The computational load per classification window amounts to 3,271,680 synaptic operations, obtained by summing the per-layer connection counts (Table 2) over 180 time steps. Exploiting input sparsity, the accelerator skips groups of four inactive synapses, reducing the effective execution cycles according to Equation 4,

$$cycles = \frac{ops \times (1 - sparsity_hw)}{modules \times parallel_spikes} \quad (4)$$

where $modules = 2$ denotes the number of neuron modules, $parallel_spikes = 4$ is the number of weights accumulated per cycle per module, and $sparsity_hw$ quantifies the fraction of four-synapse groups entirely skipped due to input inactivity (Section 5.3). In the worst case (zero sparsity), the 3,271,680 operations require approximately 409,000 execution cycles, corresponding to 17 ms at the 24 MHz system clock, already orders of magnitude below the inter-window interval imposed by the 6-second window duration and 50% overlap. The actual inference time and energy consumption, which depend on the measured spike sparsity, are reported in Section 5.3.

Between classification windows, the system enters a low-power standby state in which only the encoding slot and the sensor interface remain active, further reducing the average power consumption over extended swimming sessions.

The complete classification pipeline, from delta encoding of raw IMU samples to swimming style prediction, executes entirely within the FPGA fabric through the dedicated encoding, accelerator, and decoding modules. The RISC-V core is limited to supervisory duties (sensor communication, output transmission, and system initialization), ensuring deterministic inference latency and enabling duty-cycling during standby periods.

5 Experimental Results

This section presents the experimental evaluation of the proposed swimming style classification system. We first report LOSO cross-validation results with an analysis of per-swimmer variability and temporal voting, then compare with state-of-the-art approaches, and conclude with an analysis of spike sparsity and hardware performance.

Table 4. LOSO cross-validation results (40 folds). Per-window: each 6-second window is classified independently. Temporal voting selects the majority class over a sliding window spanning approximately 6 seconds. Accuracy and F1 follow the per-swimmer averaging methodology of Brunner et al. [1].

Configuration	Accuracy (%)	F1
Without augmentation (baseline)	89.70	0.880
Per-window (with augmentation)	94.98	0.936
+ Temporal voting (6 s)	96.27	0.945

Fig. 4. Per-swimmer accuracy distribution under 40-fold LOSO cross-validation. Both configurations use 8-bit quantized weights. *Baseline*: per-window classification without augmentation. *Final*: with oversampling, data augmentation, and temporal voting. Each data point represents a single held-out swimmer.

5.1 LOSO Cross-Validation

Under the 40-fold LOSO protocol described in Section 3.4, the proposed system achieves 94.98% mean accuracy (standard deviation 4.79% across swimmers) and an F1 of 0.936 on per-window classification, where each 6-second window is classified independently.

The per-swimmer accuracy distribution (Figure 4) shows that data augmentation substantially reduces the number of outliers compared to the unaugmented baseline. Without augmentation, six swimmers fell below 80% accuracy; with augmentation and temporal voting, only one swimmer (S11: 79%) remains below this threshold. The previously worst-performing swimmer (S33, 14% without augmentation) reaches 93% accuracy thanks to the combination of oversampling and random axis flipping. Former outliers S13, S9, S6, and S36 improve by 17–32 percentage points each, confirming that class imbalance was a primary driver of their poor performance.

Fig. 5. Normalized confusion matrix pooled across all 40 LOSO folds (per-window predictions, without temporal voting). Rows represent true labels and columns represent predicted labels. Values indicate the fraction of windows of each true class assigned to each predicted class.

Table 5. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods on the Brunner et al. dataset [1] under LOSO cross-validation. [†]Evaluated on 5 classes (including transitions); our model classifies 4 swimming styles. *Per-class accuracy of 97.4–98.8% reported; F1 not available. **Not reported by the authors; estimated from the described architecture (see text).

Method	Type	Parameters	LOSO F1
Brunner [1]	CNN	~128K	0.974 [†]
Tarasevicius [17]	Bi-LSTM	0.5–2M**	0.914 [†]
Meng [14]	CNN	≥200K**	–* [†]
Ours	SNN (LIF)	18K	0.945

Applying temporal majority voting over a sliding window of approximately 6 seconds improves mean accuracy to 96.27% and F1 to 0.945 (Table 4).

Figure 5 presents the confusion matrix pooled across all 40 folds. Freestyle, the most represented style in the dataset (39/40 swimmers), achieves the highest per-class accuracy. Butterfly, which is absent in 17 out of 40 swimmers, exhibits the lowest recall due to limited training diversity. The dominant confusion pattern involves freestyle being misclassified as other styles (or vice versa) in swimmers whose stroke mechanics deviate from the population norm.

5.2 Comparison with State of the Art

Table 5 compares the proposed SNN with the three methods evaluated on the same dataset under LOSO cross-validation. The CNN of Brunner et al. [1] achieves the highest F1 of 0.974, followed by the Bi-LSTM of Tarasevicius and Serackis [17] at 0.914 and the enhanced CNN of Meng [14] (per-class accuracy 97.4–98.8%, F1 not reported). Our SNN achieves an F1 of 0.945 with temporal

voting, narrowing the gap with the Brunner baseline to approximately 3 percentage points.

The residual gap can be attributed to several factors. Brunner et al. classify five classes (including transitions) versus our four swimming styles, and their CNN uses z-score normalization computed across the full dataset, which may capture a broader input distribution than our per-sensor physical-unit normalization (designed to prevent information leakage across folds). Additionally, our model is the only approach in the comparison that applies 8-bit weight quantization at inference time.

Despite the accuracy gap, the proposed SNN offers substantial advantages in efficiency. With 18,176 parameters, our model is approximately $7\times$ smaller than the Brunner CNN ($\sim 128\text{K}$ parameters), which is the most directly comparable baseline as it achieves the highest F1 in the comparison with a fully specified architecture. The remaining methods do not report their parameter counts explicitly; from the described architectures, we estimate 0.5–2M parameters for the Tarasevicius Bi-LSTM [17] (depending on weight sharing across the nine sensor streams) and at least 200K for the six-layer CNN of Meng [14]. In all cases, the proposed SNN is at least one order of magnitude smaller, and its compact footprint enables deployment on ultra-low-power FPGA hardware as detailed in Section 4.

5.3 Sparsity and Hardware Performance

A key advantage of SNN-based inference is the inherent sparsity of spiking activity, which reduces the number of synaptic operations that must be physically executed on the hardware accelerator. The overall sparsity across network layers and time steps is quantified according to Equation 5,

$$Sparsity = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} s_{itj}}{\sum_{i=1}^L N_i \cdot T} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where L is the number of layers, T is the number of time steps per window, N_i is the number of output neurons in layer i , and $s_{itj} \in \{0, 1\}$ is the spike output of neuron j in layer i at time step t . The measured sparsity of the swimming classification model, averaged over all LOSO test sets, is 73.6%.

As described in Section 4, the SYNtzulu accelerator processes spikes in groups of four, meaning that only groups of four consecutive inactive neurons at a given time step translate into actual computation savings. To capture this constraint, we define the hardware-aware sparsity in Equation 6,

$$Sparsity-hw = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{k=1}^{G_i} a_{itk}}{\sum_{i=1}^L G_i \cdot T} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where $G_i = \lceil N_i/4 \rceil$ is the number of four-neuron groups in layer i and $a_{itk} = 1$ if at least one neuron in group k of layer i is active at time step t , and 0 otherwise. To maximize this metric, neurons within each layer are reordered by their average

Table 6. Execution and power characteristics of the swimming classification system deployed on the iCE40-UltraPlus at 24 MHz. The energy per classification refers to a single 6-second window of 180 time steps.

Metric	Value
Synaptic operations / window	3,271,680
Hardware-aware sparsity	54.2%
Inference time	7.8 ms
Average power (during inference)	12.0 mW
Energy per classification	93.6 μ J

firing rate measured on the training set, clustering inactive neurons into the same groups; this permutation is mathematically equivalent (identical predictions) and only affects the physical layout seen by the accelerator. The measured hardware-aware sparsity after reordering is 54.2%, representing the fraction of computation that can be effectively skipped during inference.

Applying the measured sparsity-hw to the execution time model of Equation 4, the 3,271,680 synaptic operations per classification window result in an effective execution time of 7.8 ms at the 24 MHz system clock. Combined with the measured average power consumption of 12.0 mW during active inference (Table 6), the energy per classification amounts to 93.6 μ J.

All accuracy figures reported in this work refer to 8-bit quantized inference; the weight quantization (Section 3.3) reduces on-chip storage to 18.4 KB.

These figures compare favorably with conventional inference solutions. Yeon et al. [18] demonstrated 21.1 ms total inference for general activity recognition on an Apple Watch GPU with approximately 7 million parameters, implying an energy cost per inference over one order of magnitude higher than our FPGA implementation.

6 Conclusion

This work presented the first neuromorphic approach to swimming style classification, combining delta modulation encoding of multi-sensor IMU data with a compact fully connected SNN deployed on a low-power FPGA. The system classifies four swimming styles from wrist-worn smartwatch data with approximately seven times fewer parameters than the leading CNN baseline.

Evaluated on a publicly available benchmark of 40 swimmers under LOSO cross-validation, the system achieves an F1 of 0.945 with temporal voting, approximately 3 percentage points below the CNN baseline of Brunner et al. [1]. The proposed SNN operates at a fundamentally different efficiency regime: the entire model fits within on-chip SPRAM on the Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA, achieving real-time inference in 7.8 ms with 93.6 μ J per classification, over one order of magnitude below the energy cost of conventional alternatives.

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